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Jargons of Dota Player: A Language Inquiry

Chaikah S. Navare,* Onorio P. Cagoco

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study focused on the observable phenomena of Jargons of DOTA Players of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Moreover, it discussed the experiences of DOTA players as to the usage of particular language. The qualitative type of phenomenal research was done using in-depth interviews and focus group discussion among 14 participants, DOTA Players of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. There were seven (7) informants who faced the in-depth interviews and the remaining seven (7) were for focus group discussion. Through the in-depth interviews and focus group discussion, it was gathered that the participants considered peer influences, playing DOTA for recreation, the zeal of winning, getting hooked with playing DOTA, playing DOTA as escape from problems, a language expression, DOTA language as jargon for DOTA players, and exclusive use of the language, in holistically learning the jargons of DOTA. The result of the investigation showed the informants and the participants encountered challenges in learning DOTA language.

Keywords: *DOTA, jargons of DOTA, language expression*

Introduction

Jargon is a social variation which is used limitedly by current groups of social. Not everyone can understand it, because it is often such as secret words for other people out of group. In addition, some people sometimes have a miscommunication in conversation because they do not understand well what they mean in certain words of a certain community. As such, jargon is commonly used by groups that have similar interest. Gamers do not communicate directly, but they use chatting language for communication. Through chatting, gamers have their own language that only can be understood by them. This language is considered as unique and very useful to communicate effectively while they playing the game. In a study, it was revealed that there are 59 jargons found in chatting particularly playing Defense Of the Ancient (Chaer & Agustina, 2010; Setiawan, 2015).

Defense Of The Ancient (DOTA), being slowly considered as a culture for both hardcore gamers and amateur gamers alike, have formed a language that is exclusive to DOTA players, and with the formation of this language, the grammar of DOTA players changed, and the way they use DOTA terms have continued to evolve since to suit their personality and develop a trademark both for themselves and for the DOTA Community (Ali, 2011).

Moreover, Indonesian found out that there are some English words that have different meaning as commonly people know like "noobs" and "GG". These words sometimes used by Indonesian DOTA players' community to communicate between other members of community, not only in the chatting room of the game, but also in their daily conversation. Indonesian emphasizes the importance of English jargon in their daily communication as well in the community (Suwito, 2010).

Also, the use of the term "creative game talk," which refers to the way that computer game players show innovation in the way they talk to one another which is the jargon of the DOTA players being used. This is seen through word play, naming, use of popular culture references and the images and logos that players use in the context of the game DOTA. Philippine DOTA players is done through the analysis of text, which is used by players during game. This text is commonly referred to as in-game chat, and may be directed towards teammates, or allies, or everyone in the game. Interpretation of in-game chat was possible due to the researcher's direct experience with playing the game, where they can made and have a creative and fun game talk through in-game chat (Wright et al., 2012).

Indeed, according to Rodriguez, one of the DOTA players of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte and experienced the language being used by DOTA players, he knows and learns new languages which he only encountered in playing DOTA. New terms and terminologies were acquired and able to use it in different ways. Playing DOTA was also his past time and to release stress. It was his avenue to feel better and feel pleasure.

Thus, we found out that playing DOTA is a dominant game particularly in Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Most of them spend their leisure time playing online games, specifically DOTA or Defense of The Ancient. Also, we observed that most of the studies about jargons of DOTA came from international researchers. By that, we would like to conduct this kind of study wherein it focuses on the local DOTA players and the language they used.

Research Questions

The study looked into the language of DOTA players of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What are the experiences of DOTA players?
2. What are the morpho-semantic features of jargon used by DOTA players?

3. What are the insights of DOTA players on the language they used?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized a qualitative research design in phenomenological approach. We, researchers, used qualitative research format which is the study of things in their natural settings, tempting to make sense of or interpret phenomena in terms of the meanings people bring to them. Qualitative research is an inquiry approach useful for exploring and understanding central phenomenon (Denzin, 2009).

The purpose of qualitative research is to adequately interpret social phenomena. The goal of using qualitative research is to describe and explain physical and mental abuse in terms of its meaning in the lives of people living in their specific social context (Kacen, 2005).

Thus, Defined Qualitative research is defined as umbrella term covering an array of interpretative techniques which seeks to describe, decode, translate, and otherwise come to terms with the meaning, not the frequency of certain more or less naturally occurring phenomena in the social world (Al- busaidi, 2006).

Furthermore, qualitative research is conducted in a natural setting and involves a process of building a complex and holistic picture of the phenomenon of interest as well as being inductive in nature and depends on the purposeful selection of the participants. They also expressed that qualitative research consists of a set of interpretative, material practices that makes the world visible. The world into a series of representations, including field notes, interview, conversation, photographs, and recordings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2000).

In congruence, qualitative approach deals with how different people make sense in their lives. It focuses on their meaning or their perspective of particular phenomena. Some researchers go back to their participants with videotapes, audiotapes or drafts of research reports in order to capture the participants' meaning-making more accurately (Gubrium & Holstein, 1997).

As added by the natural setting is the direct source of information and the researcher is the key instrument in qualitative research. This type of research method gathered information in the form of words through interview and recordings rather than the population number of the participants. Qualitative researchers deploy a wide range of interconnected interpretive practices, hoping always to get a better understanding of the subject matter at hand (Fraenkel & Wallen, 2006).

In connection, phenomenology is a philosophical movement that approaches the study of human beings and their culture differently from the logical positivist model used in the natural sciences and in special education. Phenomenologists view the application of the logical positivist model to the study of human beings as inappropriate because the model does not address the uniqueness of human life (McPhail, 1995).

Moreover, phenomenology is a reflection on the lived experience of human existence, in the sense that reflecting on experience must be thoughtful, and as much as possible, free from theoretical, prejudicial and suppositional intoxications (Manen, 2007).

Apparently, the researchers will conduct focus group discussion and in- depth interview in order to get the details on the experiences from the informants in Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. This research commonly involves human interaction to give their different perception and express what they felt whenever they are using the jargons of DOTA players in communicating with other players.

Lastly, our research has its deep interaction for us to grasp the experiences from the participants. The information that was collected was elucidated in the context of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte.

Participants

The researcher had key informants for her phenomenological study from Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. There were 14 informants that were included in her research. Seven of which were for the in-depth interview and the other left seven were for the focus group discussion.

The selected and identified number of respondents involved in her research was supported by the article that there are at least six participants for the in-depth and at least another six for focus group discussion in a qualitative study is enough to reach the saturation point where themes are extracted (Mason, 2010).

There were seven players chosen from Barangay Maniki to participate in a focus group discussion. They served as the key and the living witness in the experiences that happened. The chosen participants were truly DOTA players who also shared the jargon they were using in playing DOTA. The other seven were also from barangay Maniki for the in-depth interview. The players were the source of information to sort out and ascertain in order to inquire languages through the jargons of DOTA players.

The participants of this study were selected based on the following pre- inclusion criteria: DOTA players who sport mastery in utilizing the jargons of DOTA daily at a minimum of five hours per day with more than three years of experience in playing DOTA.

Moreover, the players were also selected from different places in Maniki, Kapalong so for the study to reflect a more realistic finding. All of this was done to ensure the quality of the conduct as well as the findings of the study.

Procedure

She takes specific steps in collecting our data and relevant information for her study. Before the conduct of the study, she started first asking verification from her research adviser. We discussed each function in the process of conduct. We also tackled the materials to be needed in conducting the study such as questionnaires, gadgets and any other devices to be used.

There were important devices used during the conduct of the study such as a camera, video camera, and voice recorder that will serve as important instruments for the foundation of strong evidence. All written information along with their expressions was recorded solely from the point of view of the informants.

The camera was one of the useful devices that is used in the interview for it can give a substantial basis for the emotion of bodily language and facial expressions which will serve as the pillar for the research through the expressivity of strong points in the process of the interview.

Another device was the video camera is for the detailed observation of the interview, like the camera it also showed the emotions of the informants upon how they expressed their answers only that the video camera gives more detailed information that the camera cannot give, which is also the reason why it is used in the study. The video camera supplemented more vivid imagery of the interview process.

Also, a voice recorder was also a very important technological device used in the interview, although it cannot give pictures and record the informant's facial expressions still it contributes limpidity in recording that essentially serves the study.

All the three instruments were used in the conduct of the study which are all expressed above hence, this research, images, projection of emotions and expressions justify the study.

After the interview, the retrieved documents will help her to have lucid vision in unveiling the phenomenon happening in the students. Through this manner, each tape-recorded interview was transcribed verbatim to ensure greater degree of accuracy during the data analysis.

The researcher conducted an in-depth interview and focus group discussion among the DOTA players. The gathered data were subjected for treatment and interpretation. Relevant information was presented in the following chapters to give a clear view about the undergone research.

The results of the interview were presented, transcript and discussed using NVIVO for the organization. The information was analyzed, explored and treated based on the problems of the study. In order to concretize idea, the results were supported with related studies and literature.

Data Analysis

Highlighted in the systematic analysis through the retrieved document and recorded view were treated in the data analysis. The use of audio and video recorder became a tool to document the interview. The gathered documents and data were transcribed into written form. As defined by Bogden and Biklen (1982), qualitative analysis as a systematically arranged the data which could be done through working, organizing, and breaking it into managing, synthesizing, searching for patterns, discussing what is important and what is to be learned thus, it required in-depth analysis of the raw data with its logical meaning of categories.

In addition, a more comprehensive analysis is the qualitative content analysis. Marying (2000) defined the first content analysis as the use of replicable and valid method for making inferences from the text to other states or properties of its source. Following the analysis of the research, all analyzed are having all the bases down from the authentic source which come from the informants.

Moreover, Budd and Thorp as cited by Hseih and Shannon (2005) stated that qualitative content analysis collection of samples usually consist purposely selected instance which reflects the research questions being investigated. The researcher needs to set aside all prejudgment bracketing his or her experiences.

This idea is necessary to keep balanced between subjectivity and objectivity. It plays attention to unique themes that illustrate the range of the meanings from the phenomenon rather than numeric significance, qualitative content analysis focuses on the characteristics of the language in communication with attention to the content or contextual meaning of the text which is why all the result that was be shown in the preceding chapters are practically based on the answers of the informants that gave the better understanding of this research.

Patton (2002) says that triangulation may involve the use of different methods, especially observation, focus groups and individual interviews, which form the data collection strategies. Focus groups and individual interviews suffer from some common methodological shortcomings since both the interviews of a kind, their distinct characteristics also result in individual strengths. It provides sources of data that validate the crosscheck the findings of the interview and triangulation strengthens a study by combining methods.

Crabtree (2008) supported the idea that triangulation is a method for validation or verification, qualitative research generally uses this technique to ensure that an account is rich, robust, comprehensive and well-developed.

Ethical Considerations

To ensure a pleasant scientific practice in research, the ethical codes were given importance in which it is observed and applied towards the informants as well as into the context that concerns with the agreement of both the participants and the researcher.

Moreover, the main concern of her study was individuals whom she does not have any relation with. Therefore, she must ensure their safety, give them full protection so that they will not lose interest in us. She followed ethical standards in conducting this study. These were the following respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent and confidentiality (Boyatzis, 1988, Mac et al., 2005)

Respect for persons needs an obligation not to exploit the weaknesses of the research participants. Self-sufficiency was avoided in order to maintain friendship, trust, and confidence among the participants and the researchers. This was done to pay respect for the individuals concerned in the study (Creswell, 2012).

Consent is another important way of showing respect to people during research. This is to instill awareness in the participants as to the objectives and purposes of the research study that they are going to be involved with. Written consent was given to them to get their approval. After getting their nod, they participated in in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. Of course, they were informed on the results and findings of the study (Creswell, 2012).

Beneficence requires a commitment to minimize risks to the research participants rather than maximizing the profits that are due to them. Anonymity of the Interviewee was kept in order not to put each participant into risks. At all times, participants were protected, so all files of information were not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

Confidentiality towards the results and findings including the safeguard of participants, coding system were used. Meaning, the participant's identities were hidden. All materials including videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and others should be destroyed after the data are being analyzed. Some of the informants were hesitant to be interviewed at first because they were afraid of what to say but because of our reassurance to them with regards to the confidentiality of their responses, they later gave us the chance and showed comfort in answering the interview questions. She was extra careful with her questions and due to respect was given importance to this study (Maree & Van Der Westhuizen, 2007). Confidentiality towards the results and findings including the safeguard of participants, coding system were used. Meaning, the participant's identities were hidden. All materials including videotapes, encoded transcripts, notes, and others should be destroyed after the data are being analyzed. Some of the informants were hesitant to be interviewed at first because they were afraid of what to say but because of our reassurance to them with regards to the confidentiality of their responses, they later gave her the chance and showed comfort in answering the interview questions. She was extra careful with her questions and due to respect was given importance to this study (Maree & Van Der Westhuizen, 2007).

Justice requires a reasonable allocation of the risks and benefits as part of the results of the research. It is very important to acknowledge the contributions of all participants as they generally become part of the success of the research. They must be given due credit in all their endeavors. They were not able to spend any amount during the interviews. Tokens were given to them as a sign of recognition for their efforts on the study (Crabtree & Bloom, 2006).

Results and Discussion

Participants

The participants of this research paper were the DOTA players of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte. As depicted in Table 1, there were fourteen (14) DOTA players involved in this study, seven for the focus group discussion and seven for the in-depth interview, and of them, eight were Bachelor of Science in Business Administration-Major in Financial Management, four were Bachelor of Agricultural Technology students, one was Bachelor of Secondary Education, and one of them was a senior high school student. They were all a DOTA players for more than 5 years and played DOTA more than 5 hours per day.

Though they came from this people, their exposure in the DOTA language is enough for them to express their own thoughts with regards to the questions that were being asked to them. This was also the main reason why the study has no gatekeeper that will connect the researchers to the informants through the language barriers.

Key Participants. In the focused group discussion, there are seven (7) participants depicted as mentioned above. To honor the confidentiality of the respondents, these persons involved were being given pseudonyms to hide the identity of the respondents.

In the focus group discussion, Spectre was a male participant whose age is 22 years old. He is a BSBA student of KCAST and a DOTA player for 8 years. Oracle is a male respondent, enrolled in KCAST. He is a BSBA student and a DOTA player for 5 years. Nyx was a male respondent of 17, first year student of KCAST. He has been a DOTA player for 9 years. Lich was a male respondent of 21, a BAT student of KCAST and a DOTA player for 5 years. Morphling was a male respondent who is a BAT student of KCAST. He is 20 years old and a DOTA player for 10 years. Gyrocopter was a male student of KCAST with the age of 20. He has been a DOTA player for 6 years. Another respondent which is a BSBA student and a player of DOTA for 5 years was became one of the informants of this research paper and the researchers hide his pseudonym is Pheonix.

Key Informants. Furthermore, the in-depth informants are being scrutinized in this study. Also, they were given pseudonyms which

come from their number tags during their interview. Alchemist is 20 years old which is a DOTA player for 8 years. He is now a second-year student of KCAST. Dazzle was a male respondent, a DOTA player and he is now a third-year student of KCAST. Clinkz was a male participant whose age is 19 years old. He is a BAT student of KCAST and a DOTA player for 5 years. Sven is a male respondent, enrolled in KCTI. He is a senior high student and a DOTA player for 3 years. Techies was a male respondent of 19, second year student of KCAST. He has been a DOTA player for 10 years. Warlock was a male respondent of 18, a BSBA student of KCAST and a DOTA player for 6 years. Another respondent, which is a BSEd student and a player of DOTA for 6 years was became one of the informants of this research paper and the researchers hid her pseudonym is Viper.

A lot of things taught us as researchers during the interview. As we looked closely at our participants and informants, several unique experiences had been revealed as we dug deeper into the core of their experiences of language learner.

Table 1. *Participants of the Study*

<i>Focus Group Discussion Pseudonyms</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Number of Years in playing</i>	<i>Number of Hours in playing per day</i>
FGD1 – Spectre	22	8	16
FGD2 – Oracle	20	5	6
FGD3 – Nyx	17	9	6
FGD4 – Lich	21	5	5
FGD5 – Morpling	20	10	6
FGD6 – Gyrocopter	20	6	5
FGD7 – Phoenix	19	5	5
Total – 7			
<i>In-depth interview Pseudonyms</i>			
IDI01 – Alchemist	20	8	12
IDI02 – Dazzle	19	8	10
IDI03 – Clinkz	19	5	6
IDI04 – Sven	17	3	5
IDI05 – Techies	19	10	10
IDI06 – Warlock	18	5	8
IDI07 – Viper	19	6	5
Total – 7			
Grand Total – 14			

The focus group was quite interesting. It is when we observe a certain individual out of the things that made us as researchers evoke our curiosity. Many answers exploded. Emotions overflowed. Sometimes, the experiences and the coping mechanism are congruent to the individual endeavor; good or bad. Clashes of principles and beliefs about DOTA jargons are also depicted in this interview. However, they were moving into a common point.

Before the focus group discussion, we build rapport with our dear respondents, group date with them, getting to know about their personal backgrounds, which certainly paved away to us to get to know them better.

With these, the researcher was making ways in order to suggest the barrier between her and the informants for them to become more open to their feelings during the interview.

The Focus Group Discussion was conducted at Kayze and Xam Internet Café Audio recorders and video recorders were being used during the interview. She also verified the statements that they have through signing of the consent prepared by her.

Categorization of Data

She began her analysis with the data gathered after she finished the interview. She does the coding process after she has encoded and chunked the date into its commonalities and emerging themes in the gathered facts.

With these, she can assure that the data gathered are being dissected to build way in the right analysis of the data. Also, the emerging themes are being gathered through its different needs that lead to the core point of our research questions. Data results are being presented through tables.

In the table, she provided two (2) columns which tagged with emerging themes and core. The emerging themes are being presented as the result of the chunking and dissecting of ideas given by the key informants. However, these are all connected to the kind of major themes that are presented in the research question.

Along with the gathering of data, she made sure that the things she had written down are came from the respondents and never did we fabricated any of the statements as proposed by, trustworthiness establishes the confidence in the truth of the data that the researchers collected through the results of the interviews from the research design, informants and context defines trustworthiness as a qualitative study is the demonstration of the credibility and transferability of the data gathered. (Lablanca, 2010: Lincoln & Guba, 1994).

The challenge for the researcher now is how to maintain and remain that the contents of the study are all true and valid based upon the

data collection. Also, attain these, the means of getting the information will be prepared and will be presented to the panel of this research thus, making this research trustworthy.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of DOTA players?

As she had her interview, there were sub questions presented that will directly or indirectly lead her informants to the main question. She had also asked to elicit their concept as regards to the challenges experienced by DOTA players in the jargons they used.

During the in-depth and focus group discussion, she discovered that the core challenges that they had experienced upon playing DOTA are as follows: peer influences, playing DOTA for recreation, the zeal of winning, getting hooked with playing DOTA, and playing DOTA as escape from problems. The major themes and core of ideas for research question number 1 were presented in table 2. Table 3 shows the morpho-semantic features of jargons used by DOTA players. Further, table 4 shows the themes and core ideas on what are the insights of DOTA players on the language they used?

Table 2. Theme and Core ideas on the experiences of DOTA players

Emerging Themes	Core Ideas
Peer Influences	"Because of my friend. I was being influenced by them." "I become a DOTA player, why? influenced by friends." "Influenced by friends." "Influenced by friends" "For leisure time, for enjoyment only." "It's just not having fun that's why we played DOTA to be entertained." "There is nothing else that we can do. For past time." "For past time."
Playing DOTA for Recreation	"It is really fulfilling." "If we win, we will be happy. If we lose, we can be still happy. Whether we lose at least we enjoyed it." "I really enjoy playing DOTA" "Happy because if we will win, we can get money." "The best thing you could do is to win." "If I could do moves that make us win."
The zeal of winning	"During the time that I lead the game, we won three consecutive games during morning and won two consecutive games during evening." "To become a champion." "When I first blood him." "I don't mind it. I will never stop playing instead. It was my habit, my happiness."
Getting hooked with playing DOTA	"It depends on them as long as I am satisfied in playing DOTA. And if it's their perception, then let it be. This is my life." "For motivation only. I don't mind them." "We do not have the same line as a person that is why they relate on me." "Problems and irritation that could be all."
Playing DOTA as escape from problems	"I play DOTA to reduce boredom and forget problems." "Those irritations change into good but there are things such as irritations that instead to change it into happiness, you are more irritated because you lose the game." "The problems will fade away."

Peer Influences

It was revealed in the in-depth interview that peer influences are one of the experienced by the DOTA players. It was explained by Viper, one of the informants, that he was being influenced by his friends. He explicated that:

"Because of my friend, kanang mga barkada nako. Na'inpluwensyahan" (IDI07)

(Because of my friend, I was being influenced by them.)

It was supported by Spectre (pseudonym) who expressed her experience wherein he stated that he become a DOTA player because of being influenced by his friends. He stressed that:

"I become a DOTA player, why? Kanang influence by friends." (FGD01)

(I become a DOTA player because I was being influenced by my friends.)

They also enunciated that they also noticed the same challenges among their colleagues who had the same situation as they had. We, the researchers also observed this phenomenon since some of the members of this research group has the same situation with the informants. Even he herself can testify his experience of peer influences in playing DOTA.

Furthermore, the informants noticed the same experience of peer influences. Morpling and Gyrocopter elucidated that this influence

became the reason why he plays DOTA. They elucidated that:

"Influence by friends." (FGD05)

"Influence by friends." (FGD06)

Playing DOTA for Recreation

It was revealed in the interview that the informants such as Alchemis, experienced playing DOTA for recreation. This contributed to a great play during their leisure time.

"For leisure time, for enjoyment only." (IDI01)

Some of the informants added to the idea that playing DOTA for recreation is one of the reasons why they become a DOTA player. Dazzle, Nyx, and Lich exemplified that:

"Kuan man siya....kanang wala lang jud kay lingaw....mao ng magdula nalang mig DOTA para malingaw." (IDI02)

(it's because you don't have something to do that is why we played DOTA to be entertained.)

"Pareha lang sa iyaha, walay lingaw ba Pangpalipas oras." (FGD03)

(The same with him, for leisure time, for past time.)

"Mao rapud to ako'a, palipas oras." (FGD04)

(It's also the same, for past time.)

Furthermore, Viper, one of the informants explained that the result of the game will affect them as a person. He stated that:

"Feel nako kay kuan kanang fulfilling jud siya. Pero usahay pag kanang light gud ang dula, dili ka bad trip kanang fulfilling ug happy kay ka. Naa man pud gud times na bad trip kay ka usahay kay pildi, kanang makahinayang pero after ana balik lang gihapon." (IDI07)

(I feel that it is really fulfilling and it feels happier when the game is only light and you are in good mood. However, there are times that you feel annoyed because of losing, you regret and will drive you to try again.)

In connection, Techies and Sven (pseudonym) also added that the result of the game gives enjoyment to them:

"Kung madaog, edi malipay. Kung mapildi, edi malipay ra gihapon. Bahalag pildi atleast nalingaw ko." (IDI05)

(If we win, we will be happy. If we lose, we can be still happy. Whether I lose atleast I enjoyed it.)

"Kanang mura... kanang makawala siya sa akong kakapoy baa kay murag kanang stress kay ka sa inyong skwelahan. Kung magdula ka ana kay murag mawala ra gani, makalingaw jud siya sa akoo." (IDI04)

(It frees us from tiredness because I am too much stress in school. If you play that, it seems like it will vanish, it gives me enjoyment.)

Moreover, Nyx also experienced the same enjoyment in playing specially if there is gambling. He stated that:

"Happy lang kay kung makadaog mi kay naa may sugal." (FGD03)

(I am happy because if we will win we can get money.)

The Zeal of Winning

The result of the interview had seen that there are several players who experienced satisfying thing when they are playing DOTA. Clinkz (pseudonym) stated the most thing he had ever done as a DOTA player. He opined that:

"Kanang madaog ko, kana. Mao jud ng pinaka the best na mabuhat nimo ang madaog ka." (IDI03)

(If I will win the game. The best thing you could do is to win.)

In addition, Techies (pseudonym) expressed that to do moves that can make their team win is the best thing that a DOTA player can do. He stated that:

"Kanang maka buhat kog moves na makadaog sa amo." (IDI05)

(If I could do moves that can make us win.)

Warlock, Spectre, and Gyrocopter also experienced the feeling of being a winner. They expanded:

"Katong akoy nagdala sa game na nadaog mi, tulo ka game nyaa pagkagabie nadaog napud mi ikaduha. Kuan kaayo sila sa ako kay daog mi." (IDI06)

(During the time that I lead the game, we won three consecutive games during morning and won two consecutive games during evening.)

“To become a champion.” (FGD01)

“Na first blood nako siya.” (FGD06)

(When I killed him first.)

Getting hooked with playing DOTA

The result of the interview had seen that there are several individuals who are very interested in playing DOTA in which they neglect other’s opinion. Techies (pseudonym), one of the informants, expressed his experience upon his thoughts when somebody told him his life would be much better without playing DOTA. He stressed that:

“Dili lang nako hunahuna'on. Dili man pud ko mo-undang ug dula. Habit naman nako na, kalipay na nako.” (IDI05)

(I don't mind it I will never stop playing instead. It was my habit and my happiness)

In addition, Alchemist (pseudonym) also expressed that he just let other say something about him playing DOTA. He stated that:

“Ahhh sila bahala sila basta ako ma satisfy jud ko magdula kog DOTA ug ing-ana ilang panan-aw, bahala sila ako-a maning kinabuhi.” (IDI01)

(It depends on them as long as that I am satisfied playing DOTA and if it's their perception, then let them be. This is my life.)

Furthermore, Warlock (pseudonym) one of the informants stated that it was only for them to be motivated to stop playing but they just ignored it. He stressed that:

“Kuan ra mana. Motivation ra mana. Wala ra mana sa ako.” (IDI06)

(It's for motivation only. I don't mind it)

Oracle also expressed his experienced when someone told him that his life will be much better without playing DOTA. He stated that:

“Dill mi kapareha ug linya niya na pagkatao maong dili na siya karelata sa akoo.” (FGD02)

(We don't have the same line as a person that is why he cannot relate on me.)

Playing DOTA as escape from problems

It was clear in the gathered data that playing DOTA is one of the things that they are doing to escape from problems. It was also depicted from the data given by the informants that playing DOTA can do something for them to make them feel better.

Herewith were the actual comments of the informants with regards on the feelings they have which fades away when they are back online.

As being mentioned by Clinkz, they conquered their problems in terms of handling himself through playing DOTA which was mentioned by Clinkz,

“Mga problema or kalagot, kana lang man. (IDI03)

(Problems and irritation, that's all.)

And was supported by Alchemist, which he stated his experienced the reason why he played DOTA. He stressed that:

“Kuan pareha anang... bored gani nyaa daghan ug problema ana Idula nalang ug DOTA kay para didto nalang mapalabas baa ana.” (IDI01)

(The same with, when you are bored and you have a lot of problems. I will play DOTA to release all those things.)

In addition, Dazzle and Phoenix (pseudonym) stated their experienced regards on the feelings they have which fades away while playing DOTA:

“Kanang kalagot ma convert jud siya pero naa puy uban na ang imong kalagot kay bisan malipay ka, maglagot nalang ka kay mapildi man ka.” (IDI02)

(Those imitations change into good but there are things such as irritations that instead to change it into happiness, you are more irritated because you lose the game.)

“Mawalang kanang kuan problema baa.” (FGD07)

(The problems will be vanish.)

Research Question No. 2: What are the morpho-semantic features of jargons used by DOTA players?

In linguistics, a language can be studied through the analysis of its linguistic features. Phonology deals with sound pattern and how strings of sounds were linked together to form one phonological make-up. Morphology deals more on how word structures dominate and affect the evolution of language. Semantics deals with the meaning and on how these words denote or connote in an utterance and syntax deals with words and phrases strung together to form a structure of a sentence. However, in this study it only focuses on morphological and semantic features of this language.

Table 3. *Morpho-semantic features of jargons used by DOTA players*

<i>Term/Word</i>	<i>Meaning</i>	<i>Definition</i>
b	Back	Used to call for a retreat. A player saying "b" is usually suggesting that everyone back up or run away.
BS	Blood seeker or Bloodstone	May also be used as an acronym for "bullshit".
CC	Crowd Control	May also be used as an acronym for "bullshit".
GG	Good played	Said by either team when they are winning or losing and the match is close to ending, or when a team or a player gives up or claims victory. For example, both teams might say "gg" to congratulate each other after a hard-fought match, or a team might call out "gg" after their ally abandons in an assumption that they can no longer win.
ez	Easy	Typically said to mock the enemy team's lesser power.
noob	Weak	Knows little and have no will to learn any more.
rm	Rematch	A second match between the same contestants or teams
DGU	Don't Give Up	Initialism for Don't give up".
pro	Expert	Expert of the game
DOT	Damade Over Time	An applied effect that repeatedly inflicts damage at a regular interval for a specific duration.
FB	First Blood	Initialism for First Blood
GLHF	Good Luck/Have Fun	Usually said at the start of a game to encourage
KS	Kill Steal	It refers to the act of one hero stealing the kill of another hero that could have easily taken it themselves. Secondly, it refers to when another hero "secures" the kill if the carry or another hero could not do SO themselves. The latter meaning is also sometimes interchangeably used with the former meaning in a satirical or comedic way.
Mid	Middle	The middle of the three lanes in the map.
MS	Missing	Mentions that a particular hero has gone absent (missing) from their lane and is probably setting up for a gunk. Warning missing enemy heroes is crucial to warn your allies of a possible ambush in any of the lanes. "MIA" is an acronym for "Missing in Action"
NP	No Problem	Nature's Prophet or "no problem".
SD	Self-Denial	The willingness to forgo personal pleasures or undergo personal trials in the pursuit of the increased good of another.
GGWP	Good Game/Well Played	Use in a similar fashion as "gg". but also congratulates the enemy for skillful play.
GJ	Good Job	Typically said to compliment an ally.
HD	Hard Carry	A type of a carry hero which scales incredibly well with items and requires a substantial amount of farm to be effective.
DPS	Damage Per Second	A measure of the damage dealt by a hero or unit over one second. Usually refers to heroes with consistent damage output over a period rather than heroes with high burst damage periodically.
FF	Flash Farming	This is often the fastest method of farming, but it also allows the enemy to farm your creeps freely by their tower and can be risky, as being near the enemy tower is often an gunk, or the enemy might know exactly where you are clearing the camp closest to the lane tanking creeps and losing health.
Mute	Mute	Refers either to the effect that prevents item usage, blocking any means or of communication from a player in the game to avoid harassment.
DB	Disable	Referring to any spell, ability, or effect that otherwise prevents an enemy hero from moving, casting, and/or attacking, leaving them helpless for a short period of time or in general impeding their ability to act. See the main article for more information.
Juking	Juking	Running and weaving around trees, fog and other obstacles in such a manner to avoid and possibly escape an enemy.
Nuke	Nuke	A spell whose purpose is to deal a large amount of damage immediately or in a very short span of time. Heroes' adept at nuking are referred to as nukers
Pet	Pet	A creature that a hero can summon or convert to their side.

In Table 3, we presented the morpho-semantic features of jargons used by the DOTA players. The main terms "GG" which means Good Game. GG defined as said by either team when they are winning or losing and the match is close to ending, or when a team or a player gives up or claims victory. For example, both teams might say "gg" to congratulate each other after a hard-fought match, or a team might call out "gg" after their ally abandons in an assumption that they can no longer win. The main DOTA terms "noob" which means weak. It defines as the opponent knows little and have no will to learn any more. The main DOTA term "GGWP" which means

Good Game, Well Played. It was defined as use in a similar fashion as "gg", but also congratulates the enemy for skillful play. The main DOTA terms "b" which means back. It was defined as used to call for a retreat. A player saying "b" is usually suggesting that everyone back up or run away. The main DOTA term "ez" which means easy, It define as typically said to mock the enemy team's lesser power. The main DOTA term "MS" which means missing. It was defined as mentions that a particular hero has gone absent (missing) from their lane and is probably setting up for a gunk. Warning missing enemy heroes is crucial to warn your allies of a possible ambush in any of the lanes. "MIA" is an acronym for "Missing in Action". The main DOTA term "KS" which means Kill Steal. It referred to the act of one hero stealing the kill of another hero that could have easily taken it themselves. Secondly, it referred to when another hero "secures" the kill if the carry or another hero could not do so themselves. The latter meaning is also sometimes interchangeably used with the former meaning in a satirical or comedic way.

Research question No. 3: What are the insights of DOTA players on the language they used?

Here, we researchers would like to unfold the insights of the DOTA players of Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte with regards on the language they used. Their thoughts and opinions were based upon how they feel and what they say about the language they used.

The tailed summary was based upon the views of the informants about the certain kind of ideas they like to have. All was based in their opinion, and no other things were being summed up due to the coerced thoughts by the researcher. Both in-depth and focus group discussion are the sources of data.

Participants had their responses to their own experiences. From the answers of the participants, three major themes emerged: a language for expression and DOTA language as jargon for DOTA players.

Table 4. *Theme and Core Ideas on what are the insights of DOTA players on the language they used*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>
A Language for Expression	"We can express freely through using those term." "You can express what you've felt inside." "It could help you in expressing what you feel." "You could really express."
DOTA Language as Jargon for DOTA Players	"It is unique in a sense that only the DOTA player could understand. It was just like gay lingua which is made by gays that are intended only for them, and they are only who can understand those terms." "It is unique because it is rare." "It is unique because these terms or thoughts are intended only for DOTA." "It is unique because you can talk unfamiliar terms that only DOTA players can understand." "It is unique because you can express a language that only DOTA players can understand." "For communication. It is important for you to know to have a unity even if it is a small term because it is so useful, the player could understand it." "It is really important as a player in order to have a better understanding." "It is really important as a player in order to have a better understanding." "To understand easily."

A Language for Expression

It was revealed in the gathered data that the language used by DOTA players had a great help in expressing their thoughts and feelings. It was expressed by one of the informants who stated that using that language could help him express his thoughts and feelings. He elucidated that:

"Kuan kanang maka express jud mi gamit to na mga term." (IDI03)

(We can express ourselves freely through using those terms.)

^Viper also experienced how helpful to know the language of DOTA especially in playing:

"Kuan murag ma express jud nimo imong gusto nasa saloobin. Murag balos man gud na nimo sa imong kalaban. Mugawas napud dira ang trashtalk which is mabalsan nalang pud nimo. Kulangan man pud gud ang dula kung wala ng mga terms pati ng mga trashtalk." (IDI07)

(Maybe you can express you want and through that, You can take revenge on your opponent. There would be also the presence of trash talk wherein you can also take a repay. The game would not be complete without these terms as well as the trash talk.)

In addition, Spectre and Lich expressed their experience that through using the jargon of DOTA, they can express what they feel. They stated:

"Makapagawas sa gibati." (FGD01)

(Can express what you've felt.)

"Maka express jud ka." (FGD04)

(You can really express)

DOTA Language as jargon for DOTA players

Answers were derived from the interview supported by the data gathered through the focus group discussion. It was revealed in the conducted interview that DOTA language is unique. It was expressed by Viper, one of the informants, that DOTA language is unique which they could only understand it He stated that:

"Unique siya in terms na ang mga DOTA player lang ang nakabalo. Murag gay lingua lang gud na mga bayot ang naghimo nyaa sila rapud naka sabot. Pareha sa DOTA, dill man ang mga playerang nagbuhat pero intended gud jud na para sa ila na kanang DOTA player ray nakasabot." (IDI07)

(It is unique in a sense that only the DOTA player could understand. It was just like gay lingua which is made by gays which is intended only for them, and they are the only ones who could understand those terms.)

Lich (pseudonym) also supported the statement above stating that:

"Unique siya kay panagsaon raman siya." (FGD04)

(It is unique because it is rare.)

What makes DOTA language unique is the language itself wherein only players could understand it. In fact, it is supported by some of the participants that they found the DOTA language is different from other languages. Lich, Spectre, and Phoenix stated that:

"Unique siya kay kane siya na mga term or thoughts kay para lang man gud na sa DOTA na game." (FGD04)

(It is unique because those terms or thoughts are intended only for DOTA)

"Unique siya kay maka storya ka'g wala diri wala didto." (FGD01)

(It is unique because you can talk not here there.)

"Unique siya kay mapagawas nimo imong mga language na nahibal-an na kamo ray nakasabot." (FGD07)

(It is unique because you can express that language wherein only DOTA players can understand)

Moreover, Viper (pseudonym) one of the informants expressed her insights about the exclusive use of DOTA language. He stressed that:

"Communication jud siya. Makabalo jud dapat ka kay para naay unity bisan small term lang gud na siya kay gamit jud siya., makasabot jud ang mga player." (IDI07)

(For communication. You should know it to have a unity even if it is a small term because it is so useful, the player could understand it.)

Clinkz also expressed the importance of jargons:

"Kanang importante oyy as a player para magkasinabtanay jud." (IDI03)

(It is important as a player in order to have an understanding.)

In addition, Dazzle and Phoenix stated their experiences on how important to know the jargons of DOTA:

"Kato siya na mge term importante jud to siya kay kay nas man jud mga leader ana na dula, so wala ka kabala ato na term dili jud ka kasabot sa iya unsa iyang gipang ingon Wala moy teamwork kailangan man gud ug teamwork ana na dula gud." (IDI02)

(Those term are important because there are leaders on that game, so if you don't know the term you will never understand what he is talking about. There would be no teamwork, it really needs to have a team work on this kind of game.)

"To understand easily" (FGD07)

Conclusions

The results in the conduct of the interview in both in-depth and focus group discussion would help the DOTA players to be recognized and consider in some instances regarding their language.

This study had a great benefit in showing the jargons of DOTA players being used in playing. The people would be able to understand the environment of DOTA and how teenagers become DOTA players. Moreover, the DOTA players would have a chance to show how unique the terms they have in playing.

The results derived from interviews opened a window of understanding among the DOTA players towards the language they used. It reveals that the more they are exposed to language, the more they will know and the more they possess activeness during the game.

But it also shows that language is diverse in every society. The study of players who entered playing DOTA at more than 3 years and more than 5 hours of playing per day focuses on the language they used in playing; however, the things behind their experiences including the external factors such as trash talk and Girlfriend's factor in this study.

The future exploration in the experiences of the DOTA players at more than 3 years and more than 5 hours of playing per day as regards to their personal experiences upon entering online games may be a good study to conduct.

To validate the findings, further research may be conducted on the other group of players. This will investigate the same phenomena to make concrete activities and methodologies in dealing with the players to have better understanding of the language.

Lastly, this research made a big contribution to clarify misconception towards the language being used by the DOTA players and give understanding concerning to the jargons of DOTA.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Chaikah S. Navare

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Onorio P. Cagoco, MAEd

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines